

Captain Electric: Human Powered Electronic Garments

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Abstract: “Captain Electric” consists of three electronic garments that both passively harness energy from the body and actively allow for power generation by the user. Referencing fashion’s historic relationship between discomfort and style, the garments require effort to produce varying amounts of energy to fuel themselves and actuate light and sound events on the body. The garments, called Itchy, Sticky, and Stiff, conceptually reference safety apparel and personal protection as well as our fears of natural disasters and other states of emergency. Instead of attempting to conceal the generators and their operation, we chose to overtly integrate them into the garment concept and design so as to expose the mechanics of anxiety and physical strain.

Key words: Electronic garments, Human-generated power, Wearable technology.

1. Introduction

The three garments described in this paper constitute the final stage of the “Captain Electric and Battery Boy” research project, initiated in 2007 to explore design possibilities for wearable human generated power [3]. Initial research goals include the design and production of a collection of electronic garments that harness power from the body and use that energy to transform themselves through sound and illumination. The process is heavily informed by the desire to investigate how emotions and aesthetics come to expression in design and how new/emerging technologies can help us to articulate new questions about the relationship between electronic artifacts and the human body. Human generated power necessitates electric generators: devices that convert mechanical energy to electrical energy. In a wearable context, this implies the development of physical choreography, in the form of repetitive movements that generate energy, together with compelling placement of the generators on the body to create the opposing forces required. While the project focuses on conceptual explorations and speculative user scenarios, it also involves the development of custom circuitry and specialized solutions for integrating power generators into garments and wearable artifacts.

The three dresses we have created, called Itchy, Sticky, and Stiff, conceptually reference safety apparel and personal protection as well as our fears of natural disasters and other states of emergency. They both passively harness energy from the body and actively allow for power generation by the user. Instead of attempting to conceal the generators and their operation, we chose to overtly integrate them into the garment concept and design so as to expose mechanics of anxiety and physical strain. Referencing fashion’s historic relationship between discomfort and style, the garments require effort to produce varying amounts of energy to fuel themselves. Depending on levels of discomfort and extenuation, as well as the desire to supersede the limitations of the human body, the users are able to actuate light and sound events on the body.

Figure 1. The Captain Electric dresses: Stiff, Sticky, and Itchy

2. Garment Design

2.1. Mobile Power and Sustainability

With the proliferation of wearable and portable electronic devices in our everyday lives, our power consumption needs are constantly increasing. The development of alternative energy sources has not kept up with the needs of our markets and we find our spaces cluttered with an ever-expanding number of adaptors and chargers. A promising alternative involves the development of energy sources that are independent from our power grids and reside on the body, collocated with the electronic devices they power [5]. Research in this area includes (1) alternate power sources such as flexible solar panels, photovoltaic cells, biobatteries, and dielectric elastomers among others; (2) eco-design and design for sustainability; and finally (3) parasitic power, which involves harnessing energy directly from the body or generating power by the user. Researchers such as Paradiso from the MIT Media Laboratory have studied methods to recover power (a) passively, from body heat, arm motion, typing, and walking, and (b) actively through user actions such as winding or pedaling [5,6,7]. Many of these solutions compromise comfort in order to deliver functionality, which contributes to slow rates of acceptance both from designers and potential customers.

2.2. Design Approach

The dresses are the result of a development process that included a series of structured brainstorming and bodystorming exercises. Very early in the design process, it was decided that we would not attempt to conceal the generators and their operation. Previous work in body-generated power strives to seamlessly integrate generators into wearable artifacts so as not to make their presence “obvious or annoying” [6]. Most often, this is accomplished by harnessing the energy from walking by embedding generators in the soles of shoes [5,6,7]. We chose to pursue a different approach, one that is heavily influenced by the field of fashion design. While it is

difficult to accept an uncomfortable running shoe or other fitness garment, it is easier to embed the discomfort and the inefficiency of current human-generated power solutions into the culture of fashion and costuming. Fashion designers throughout history have distinguished themselves by presenting new silhouettes and trends that constantly surprise and challenge the body. This has been exemplified by devices that include brassieres, bustles, crinoline hoops, and exaggerated shoulder pads as well as more extreme practices that involve deliberate physical deformation of the body [4]. The field of fashion design often embraces discomfort and has been known to tolerate some amount of pain, which inspired us to explore the use of irritation and inconvenience as a means of power generation on the body. The Captain Electric garments focus on alternate definitions of functionality, such as pleasure, fun, and beauty, so as to allow playful and engaging design concepts, while leveraging the discomfort to influence the conceptual direction of the experience.

The brainstorming and bodystorming exercises were carried out over a period of two weeks during an intensive thematic workshop. We studied several power generators including a rotating dynamo with a hand crank, a cord-pulling mechanism, a coil-magnet shaking generator, a pushing device, and an assortment of small DC motors. Since we chose to overtly integrate their function into the garment concept and design, we considered different placements on the body as well as possible associated motions such as pulling, pushing, rolling, shaking, jumping, or twisting. Our exercises led us to consider complex choreographies that were influenced by contemporary dance and included unexpected, playful, abrupt, intense, passionate, forceful, and sometimes absurd movements.

Figure 2. Concepts for head/knee contraction and underarm accordions.

We developed concepts such as “instruction manuals for extremely improbable situations” and “perversely connected garments”. We eventually converged on concepts that dealt with stress, anxiety, fear, claustrophobia, and other “states of emergency.” The final designs conceptually reference safety apparel and personal protection as well as our fears of natural disasters and other states of emergency [3].

2.3. Itchy

Itchy is based on a classic fitted silhouette and is decorated with a collection of reconfigurable wool necklaces. The layering of large textural necklaces is evocative of itchy wool turtlenecks and the aesthetic of bulky jewelry. The itchiness of the wool necklaces compels the user to grasp them and start moving them on the body.

Figure 3. The illuminated Itchy neckline and detail of the white input necklace.

One of the necklaces is attached to a power generator while another one is augmented with a series of LEDs. As the user pulls and pushes on the necklace, she charges the battery and the illuminating necklace is activated. Itchy's output consists of lighting that illuminates the face. The pattern of lights that rotate around the neckline of the dress is reminiscent of safety buoys, lighthouses, and emergency sirens but their amber color is subdued and relaxing.

Figure 4. The Itchy dress.

Itchy generates power through a small servomotor. The servo-controller was removed in order to make the power generation more efficient regardless of the direction that the motor gears are turned. With a large enough handle on the motors shaft, it takes little effort to generate a decent amount of power, through the motor. Many tests were done to determine the position of the motor in order to get a sufficient range of motion to generate power. It needed to be placed behind the head of the user, a few inches out from the back of the neck. As a result, a sculptured ledge jutting out from the back was created and attached with screws and bolts through the outer layer of the dress to an inner layer, moulded to sit carefully on the shoulders. The servomotor was placed through the plastic and screwed in with rubber washers to cushion any heavy impact from the neck-wrap pulling.

The dress features broad shoulders that complement the back exoskeleton that both supports the necklaces and connects them to the PCB. All necklaces are removable and supple offering the user the ability to interact with her garment and modify her appearance. The decorative necklaces are knit of Peruvian Highland wool, mohair, nylon, organic cotton and merino wool blends on a manual-knitting machine. The texture of the leather on the input necklace facilitates gripping and pulling when attached to the generator.

2.4. Sticky

Sticky restricts the arms the wearer by tethering the dress' sleeves to the chest via pulley dynamos, embedded in hard shells on the dress. This design encourages the user to push her arms outward from the body in an attempt to free herself, thereby generating power. As the user attempts to pull, in an increasingly frantic manner, her arms from her body, the energy stored in the battery illuminates rubbery pebbles in her pocket. The illumination is amplified by the phosphorescent pigment integrated into the rubber casings that house the LEDs. The expanded kinetic energy is symbolically stored in the pocket, in the form of light energy, and the sense of claustrophobia is reinforced.

Figure 5. The Sticky dress.

The aesthetics of this dress are based on references to constraint, restriction, and even bondage. This is articulated by physically attaching the user's arms to her garment in a position of self-restraint, following the natural curvature of the female form. In an attempt to free herself, the user generates a reaction in a personal space (the pocket) that she herself cannot access. White perforated leather was selected for the front pocket

panels to allow light to shine through in a darkened environment, allowing the evidence of her movements to seep through into public space.

The pulley-dynamos are held in place on the inside of the shells with metal bracing, screwed and bolted into the plastic shells, while the handle of the pulley sticks through a slit in the hard shell. The shells are upholstered with embroidered leather and attached to the body using polyester straps and fasteners, which are concealed between the outside layer of the dress and the liner. The cylindrical dynamos are screwed into the metal bracing to ensure that the pulley string aperture is set at an ideal angle for the range of movement of the arm .

Figure 6. Dynamo, LED, and PCB integration.

2.5. Stiff

Reminiscent of the posture caused by muscular stiffness, the silhouette of this dress draws emphasis on the back and shoulders of the user. This is the primary site of interaction of the garment and closely connected to the output, located in the exaggerated hood of this dress. The hood is designed to evoke a sense of intimacy between the user and her garment. As she pushes her back against the wall or experiences pressure on her back from another user, the energy generated activates a sound recording that plays inside the hood. The audio consists of messages theoretically designed to soothe and comfort from the tension that is causing her rocking motion. The messages use impersonal therapeutic language and consist of repetitive phrases such as: “Please do not panic. Everything will be all right. Do not panic. There is no reason to panic.” As such, they tend to induce additional sense and anxiety when worn, and highlighting the very personal nature of fear and the difficulty in blanket treatments.

Conceptually, it was decided that the motion that we wanted to exploit to generate power would be one of rocking or convulsing against a wall if one were alone, or a motion similar to receiving a back massage. Essentially, the generators needed to be mounted on the back. Tests with the generators showed that they actually require quite a bit of force to push down effectively, and to generate the required amount of power. The generator used for this dress comes from a push-motion dynamo flashlight. Due to the unusual ergonomic shape of the flashlights attempts were made to remove the dynamo mechanism from the body of the flashlight, but these attempts all yielded a substantial decrease in power generating efficiency. Therefore it became necessary to integrate the entire flashlight casing into the garment.

Figure 7. Hood detail in the Stiff dress and construction details of the back piece.

We formed a solid piece that followed the contours of the back and could be strapped on like a backpack. Because of the relatively high force of impact required to generate power and the unusual shape of the flashlights, we used moulded silicone components to secure the generators in place and absorb the shock of impact. The dynamos were extended with thin plywood reinforcements to distribute any stresses caused by an accidental side impact. A 5" diameter disc was then attached to the plywood adaptor, creating a large surface to push on to generate power. In order to fill out the shape of the back, foam padding was placed between the dynamos, and a neoprene cover was made for the entire unit in order to protect the components. As with the all garments, 30 gauge Teflon coated wire was used to connect all electronics in order not to lose any power through to resistance. The generators were connected to the circuit board using snap connectors, so that they could be relatively easily replaced as needed.

Figure 8. The Stiff dress.

The outer shell of the garment is composed of white supple leather embellished with light green embroidery. Inspired by topographic cartography, the embroidery enables the mapping of pressure points located on the back. These three areas are demarcated by round spaces void of undulating lines. The topographic embroidery was achieved freehand on an industrial sewing machine. For greater tactility, two polyester threads were combined to embroider each trace.

The audio output uses small mp3 players together with a small circuit board with digital switches. All electronic components, including the wires, are placed between the lining and the leather outer shell of the top half of the garment. In order to easily access these components, the lining hangs separately from the dress and is outfitted with two invisible zippers (one located in the hood, the other in the back). In certain areas, a layer of cotton tacked at the seams of the leather exists to enable the dissimulation of these components by hanging or floating between the two. The PCB, speaker and modified mp3 player are hand stitched to this layer and their respective wires affixed by machine zigzag stitch.

3. Materials

The silhouettes we developed focus on the contrast between clean-cut lines and exaggerated organic forms. We also employed several architectural details in their construction: tucked pleats, broad shoulders, and flattened seams. We accentuated the head and neck shape thematic, leading to large hoods and necklace and used double-breasted closures to reference notions of authority, military apparel, and masculinity. The materials included a lot of leather, both for its structural and sculptural qualities and for the organic, luxurious associations. Leather lends itself to an urban aesthetic, and is very rugged and durable. The wool knit provided a high contrast with the leather, which mirrored the contrasting notions of comfort and irritation. The color palette was composed mostly of grey tones (authoritarian, urban, concrete, cold) and white (clean, modern, futuristic, soft).

We tested various generators, including a rotating dynamo, a coil-magnet shaking generator, a small DC motor, an inductive clip, and a piezo film. The table on the next pages shows initial measurements. We determined dynamos to be the most efficient but also found several servo-motors that gave us similar readings. In order to harness mechanical energy from the body into electrical energy we integrated dynamos into the dresses. These dynamos were harvested from: a push-dynamo flashlight, a pulley dynamo flashlight, and a servomotor, but were kept in their original outer shells, as there was a marked decrease in power output efficiency when attempting to relocate them.

Figure 15. The structure for the pulleys of the Sticky dress.

Integrating mechanical dynamos into clothing required special considerations. The design process began with determining the body motions that would be choreographed to generate power, and then moved on to actual physical integration. Due to mechanical stresses created by the human physical interaction with the dynamos, be it from pulling, pushing or twisting, it was discovered that hard shells needed to be embedded within the garments to hold the dynamos securely in place. However, each of the 3 actions directly related to the three garments produced, required different materials and methods to integrate, so as to minimize stress and damage, and to maximize power generation and ease of use. While operating a hand held dynamo in the form of a crank, pulley or push motion is relatively easy, as it is being securely held by one's hands, connecting the two moving ends of a dynamo to the body via clothing is far more problematic.

Material research revealed that the plastic Sintra is easily heat formed at relatively low temperatures, it machines well, it's easily worked and shaped with hand tools as well as being quite strong. All hard shells housing the generators were made from Sintra. The dynamos are composed largely of plastic and contain moving parts that have a tendency to wear out over time, and occasionally need replacing. This dictated a modular design approach, whereby all input (dynamos) and output components (LEDs and MP3 players), would need to be integrated through the use of a variety of fasteners, such that they could be easily swapped out in case of damage.

3.1. Electronic Design

We are using three distinct methods for harnessing kinetic energy from the human body, transforming it into electric energy, and storing it on a power cell integrated into the garments. In all three cases, the kinetic energy is harnessed using inductive generators. The induced electric energy is fed into an accumulator that takes care of rectifying the voltage and storing the energy into a Li-Ion battery cell. A microcontroller monitors the stored energy and wakes up when enough power is accumulated into the battery to animate the garments in two different ways.

The inductive generators harness kinetic energy from three distinct body movements. One transforms the action of *pushing* with a linear gear that actuates a series of circular gears to make a motor turn. Another transforms the action of *rolling* with a series of circular gears to make a motor turn. The third transforms the action of *pulling* with a pulley system that again makes a motor turn.

3.2. Programming

In order to simplify the programming of the circuit boards, some basic firmware was created that would allow one to monitor the power input from the dynamos, and to compare that to the level in the battery. This allows us to activate and deactivate the output of the dresses based on the amount of power produced without allowing the battery the drain fully, which can eventually be detrimental in attempting to recharge it. The comparative threshold can be adjusted depending on the power requirements of the output of the specific garment.

Itchy's output consists of a pattern of lights that rotate around the neckline of the dress. The pattern mimics the motion required to power the LEDs. The programming for the LEDs uses PWM firmware designed for this particular project. Sticky has the simplest programming. The output of the dress consists of glowing 'pebbles'. LEDs embedded in Dragon Skin tinted with blue phosphorescent pigments are integrated and embroidered into one of the pockets of the dress. As the user pulls her arms away from her body, the energy generated is stored in the battery. The programming consists simply of turning on the LEDs embedded in the pebbles as long as there is sufficient power to do so. Stiff's output, as the user pushes her back against the wall or interacts with another

person, consists of therapeutic audio messages theoretically designed to soothe one from the tension that is causing her rocking motion. The messages tend to be overly specific and somewhat stress inducing, inciting a sense of anxiety when worn, and highlighting the very personal nature of fear and the difficulty in blanket treatments.

5. Acknowledgement

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6. Conclusions

The three “Captain Electric” garments demonstrate a possible direction for the integration of human-generated power modules into wearable artifacts. Instead of attempting to conceal power generators and their operation, we propose to overtly integrate them into product concepts and designs. This approach is much closer to the field of fashion and industrial design and exploits elements of the playful and the unexpected, which are valuable factors in the design of successful products.

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